

NIMA: Near In-Memory High-Precision Accumulation Unit for Heterogeneous Analog/Digital Deep Learning Acceleration

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Abstract—Analog In-Memory Computing (AIMC) crossbars often face size limitations that hinder the mapping of entire neural network layers onto a single AIMC Tile. To overcome this, layers are typically distributed across multiple tiles or within a tile by multiplexing different sets of weights at various time intervals. However, this generates partial sums that must be accumulated along the bit lines to produce the final output, underscoring the need for integrated accumulation capabilities within AIMC systems. In this work, we propose a Near In-Memory High-Precision Accumulation Unit (NIMA) with built-in internal tile and external tile accumulation functionality, positioned at the periphery of the AIMC crossbar. This unit leverages the affine correction capabilities of existing systems and ensures high precision during partial sum accumulation. We have physically implemented NIMA in a 14nm CMOS technology, providing comprehensive performance and area evaluations and comparison with the prior art. We investigate and compare different layer mappings and accumulation schemes supported by the proposed unit, evaluating both latency and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). We further assess the precision of the proposed unit on large layers of ResNet9 and ResNet32 for image classification on CIFAR10/CIFAR100 datasets.

Index Terms—Analog in-memory computing, near-memory computing, partial sum accumulation, deep neural network inference

I. INTRODUCTION

Analog In-Memory Computing (AIMC) has emerged as a promising alternative to the traditional Von Neumann model by performing computations directly in memory. In AIMC, weights remain stationary on the memory array, enabling efficient execution of Matrix-Vector Multiplications (MVMs) with minimal data transfer [1]. Since MVMs are fundamental in Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), AIMC’s ability to accelerate these operations makes it highly suitable for DNN inference.

AIMC tiles are typically composed of a memory crossbar that encodes the matrix elements (e.g., weights of DNN layers) into conductance/resistance values of memory devices, a series of Digital-to-Analog Converters (DAC) that encode the input vector (e.g., input activations) to voltage pulses, to be further applied to the memory crossbar, and a series of Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADC) responsible for translating the resultant current, voltage or charge of the multiplication into output vectors (e.g. output pre-activations). Each ADC output is representative of the dot product between the matrix and an input vector. The AIMC tiles are complemented with near-memory logic, digital accelerators, and on-chip memory to support end-to-end deep learning models [13].

Prior studies demonstrated AIMC hardware macros with relatively large memory crossbars [3], [4], [9]. Yet, many mid-size and large-scale DNN layers cannot fit into a single tile in certain instances. In the case of tall weight matrices, the partial sums can be computed by different AIMC tiles and should be added at the near-memory digital periphery or in a specialized Digital Processing Unit (DPU). This *External Tile Accumulation (ETA)* can also be used for residual connections. Additionally, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) workloads often employ weight replication to optimize latency and area utilization as feature maps progressively shrink. Yet, partial sums generated during this process are often overlooked [6].

In another scenario, instead of processing outputs across multiple tiles, partial sums can be generated within a single tile. AIMC tiles can often be subdivided into smaller regions, with each region assigned a portion of the weight matrix, or a *weight set*. For example, since ADCs consume significant area and power [3], a larger AIMC tile (e.g., 256×2048) can be combined with fewer ADCs (e.g., 256) by using time-multiplexing. Each time-multiplexed output represents a partial sum produced by a corresponding weight set. These partial sums can be combined then via (*In-Tile Accumulation (ITA)*). This concept also applies to 3D tiles, such as 3D NAND Flash, where only one physical layer of a 3D tile is actively in use at a time [15], [17]. A single weight matrix can be mapped across multiple physical memory layers of a 3D tile in forms of weight sets, with partial results obtained layer-by-layer.

To support these diverse functionalities for a flexible implementation at the AIMC tile periphery, we propose a compact Near In-Memory High-Precision Accumulation Unit (NIMA), consisting of affine correction, re-quantization and accumulation blocks where the latter provides support for both ITA and ETA. This fixed-precision unit is tailored to minimize the area, which is particularly attractive for resource-constraint edge systems while ensuring floating-point-comparable precision.

II. THE PROPOSED NIMA

A. NIMA microarchitecture

The proposed NIMA is a fully parametric unit consisting of three primary blocks: the fixed-point affine correction, re-quantization, and accumulation logic. Its parametric nature allows NIMA to interface flexibly with various AIMC tile configurations. Figure 1 illustrates the NIMA datapath and

Fig. 1: NIMA microarchitecture.

interface with an AIMC tile. In this work, we investigate an architecture that integrates 8 NIMA units at the periphery of a 2D non-volatile memory array of size 256×2048 leveraging analog weight storage and 256 ADCs. This translates in each AIMC tile having 8 weight sets that can be time-multiplexed across a single ADC. With 256 ADCs available, each NIMA processes up to 32 time-multiplexed ADC outputs and supports all the necessary parameters (i.e. α , γ , and η) to apply the affine correction. Since the maximum number of weight sets is set to 8, each NIMA supports up to 7 ITAs, requiring distinct affine correction parameters per weight set. Additionally, the same configuration, i.e. accumulator size, allows to support up to 7 ETAs. To support this, each NIMA includes 7 re-quantization parameter sets (α_{acc} , γ_{acc} , η_{acc}). The notation (a,b) in Fig. 1 denotes the integer and fractional part of these parameters. The inter-tile communication is done via an 8-byte bit-parallel interconnect.

Fixed-point affine correction: The affine correction operation is commonly employed in AIMC systems to address both variability across ADCs [8] and device noise, such as temporal conductance drift and temperature sensitivity [5], [7]. The affine correction procedure mitigates these by applying simple per-column scale and offset adjustments and can be seamlessly integrated with core CNN operations like Batch Normalization (BN). To enable full support for end-to-end CNN models, it is common to incorporate an additional Rectified Linear Unit

(ReLU) operation within the same digital block. The affine correction datapath used in our architecture is based on an existing design that incorporates all of these features [8].

Re-quantization: DNN accelerators frequently support lower precision activations, particularly INT8 for energy and memory efficiency [14], and the communication fabric in AIMC-based accelerators are often customized for reduced precision data [3], [13]. Consequently, when an accumulation operation is required between activations from different tiles, partial sums are quantized to a lower precision. When handling ETA, a re-quantization step is necessary to align values to the same arithmetic range. This step involves a simple scale and offset correction applied to the transmitted data.

Accumulation logic: The *accumulation & output* stage follows the correction stage in the NIMA data processing pipeline. A Register Array (RA) is placed to store the intermediate accumulation values, and its size depends on the accelerator constraints. For instance, the RA depth depends on the number of columns time-multiplexed across a single ADC; while the RA width depends on the output precision of the AIMC tile and on the number of accumulations that needs to be supported. In the proposed design, each NIMA can time-multiplex the output of 32 ADCs, each time-multiplexing 8 weight sets, and supports 7 accumulations of 8b, 2's complement numbers. This requires a minimum of 11b to represent intermediate and final accumulation values without loss of information. Consequently, for the NIMA design, the selected RA depth is 32×8 , with a width of 11b. Throughout the accumulation steps, intermediate values are maintained in 11b, and only upon finalizing the accumulation, the output is downsized to match the data bandwidth of the communication mesh, i.e. 8b in this work. This downsizing is achieved by truncating the data starting from the Least Significant Bit (LSB) to minimize quantization error with minimal computational overhead. After the accumulation logic, an optional ReLU is placed.

B. Layer Mapping and Different Accumulation Schemes

A multi-tile architecture with NIMA positioned at the periphery of each AIMC array leads to a variety of possible layer mappings. Figure 2 visualizes a few of the representative layer mappings for a tall layer being represented with 8 weight sets. **MapA** shows the ITA-only flow (7ITA), where the affine correction block is re-used sequentially each time a partial sum is generated, and the intermediate sum is accumulated and stored in the RA. An alternative is the ETA-only case (7ETA) shown in **MapD**, where the affine correction path is first applied within each individual tile to generate a partial sum. When performing the accumulation, at each time step, a new tile acts as the receiver for the data streams, while the other one as a transmitter, building a chain [3]. Data transmitted to the receiving tile is re-quantized using the re-quantization block before the accumulation. The affine correction and re-quantization can be performed *in parallel*, as both pipes are designed to have distinct data pointers to the internal RA.

Besides these two modes, *mixed accumulation* schemes can interleave ITA and ETA loops. In **MapB**, 3ITAs are first per-

Fig. 2: Layer mapping and accumulation schemes. Red and blue arrows indicate ITA and ETA, respectively.

formed in each tile and then the output of Tile1 is sent to Tile0 which performs a single ETA. In **MapC**, the flow is similar, but each tile performs 1ITAs and maximum 1ETA. In this case, since all the tile outputs need to be accumulated, 3ETAs are executed in a chain manner by the NIMA of Tile0, Tile1, and Tile2. Performing ITAs first leverages NIMA capabilities of preserving high precision for partial sum accumulation and minimizes the need for downsizing operations, thereby reducing overall quantization error.

III. RESULTS

A. Evaluations on Layer Mappings

In this section, we evaluate NIMA latency and MAE implications of synthetic ADC outputs for the accumulation schemes described in Fig. 2. Figure 3(a) shows the latency evaluation for the mentioned accumulation schemes for four different matrix sizes per weight set (with 8 weight sets in total) when considering 8 NIMAs per tile. In **MapA**, the latency increases in a near-exponential manner with the matrix size due to the dependence on the number of time-multiplex columns per ADC. As the number of ETAs increase (from **MapA** to **MapD**), the parallelization of NIMAs also increases, therefore, leading to a more gradual increase in latency with each matrix size scaling. Figure 3(b), evaluates the latency and the MAE for different ratios of $\#ETA/(\#ETA+\#ITA)$, with a fixed crossbar size per weight set of 256×256 . The weight sets per AIMC tile are iterated from 2 to 16, and the MAE of each scheme is measured against an FP16 baseline. A trade-off is observed between latency and MAE as the ratio $\#ETA/(\#ETA+\#ITA)$ increases, with the speed-up primarily resulting from NIMAs parallelization. To optimize the speed-up and precision balance, mixed-accumulation schemes become favorable, especially when using more weight sets.

B. Evaluation on CNN Models

Here, we assess the performance of the proposed NIMA by analyzing the layer-wise L1 error and latency for two CNN models, namely ResNet9 [11] (on CIFAR10) and ResNet32 [12] (on CIFAR100).

1) **Layer-wise accuracy:** We evaluate the L1 error for different numbers of intermediate accumulations for the layers that require partial sum accumulations. We use simulated ADC data from the AIMC prototype macro presented in [2]. We

Fig. 3: (a) NIMA latency as a function of the memory array size. (b) NIMA latency and MAE for different ratios of number of ETA over total number of accumulations.

compare the NIMA schemes with a *baseline* implementation adopted in [3], which employs an ETA-only scheme in FP16, downsizing each intermediate accumulation result to 8b and sending it to the next tile in a chain fashion for further accumulation. In ResNet9, only two layers require one partial sum accumulation; we consider both the 1ITA and 1ETA schemes. In the ResNet32 model, ten layers require one partial sum accumulation (ResNet32_1ACC), whereas nine layers require two partial sum accumulations (ResNet32_2ACC). As shown in Figure 4, when the number of accumulations is 1, the ETA scheme proposed in this work overlaps with the baseline, whereas ITA improves the L1 error $5.9\text{-}33.3\times$ compared to ETA. When the number of accumulations to be performed is 2, ITA improves the layer-wise L1 error by $7.1\text{-}33.3\times$.

2) **Layer-wise latency evaluation:** In this section, we focus on one of the ResNet32 layers that require 3 partial sums accumulations and evaluate the latency of executing such a layer when the NIMA block is used in conjuncture with AIMC tiles. We focus on a portion of a heterogeneous accelerator consisting of 3 AIMC tiles, each equipped with 8 NIMAs operating in parallel, as described in Section II-A, and a DPU [16], with 8-byte parallel processing capabilities. The accelerators utilize a 2D mesh as interconnect with 8B/cycle bandwidth. We select the layer CONV3_0_2, split it into three matrices, each having 64 columns, and consider the 2ITA, 2ETA, 1ITA_1ETA configurations.

Figure 5 shows the overall execution time of the selected layer as a function of the AIMC tile integration time. As expected, the tile integration time significantly affects the ITA approach since each accumulation can only be performed after the integration, and there is no parallelization. Instead, using the ETA scheme offers up to 1.6x latency improvements. This

Fig. 4: Layer accuracy studies on ResNet9/ResNet32.

Fig. 5: Latency study on ResNet32 layer CONV3_0_2.

is because multiple NIMAs enable pipeline accumulation and post-processing operations, reducing the amount of time the digital units are on. In contrast, the DPU approach handles post-processing near the tile periphery and accumulates data separately in a specialized unit. This separation leads to serialization of the two operations, increasing overall latency compared to the ETA scheme. The latency improvement with ETA in comparison to the DPU approach is up to $2.2\times$ when leveraging larger AIMC parallelization capabilities, e.g. with a larger array with 512 columns per weight set.

C. Synthesis of the NIMA

We synthesize the proposed NIMA unit using Cadence Genus 20.11 and perform physical implementation using Cadence Innovus 21.13 in a 14 nm CMOS technology. Table I summarizes the Power, Performance and Area estimations. The affine correction / re-quantization / accumulation blocks contribute 7.4% / 6.8% / 40.1% to the NIMA area, respectively.

IV. COMPARISON WITH THE STATE OF THE ART (SOTA)

Table I compares NIMA with recent near-memory post-processing units featuring accumulation support. Notably, NIMA addresses precision loss during accumulation by adopting high precision accumulation, unlike other designs that maintain a fixed bit-width for intermediate results and input/output precision. By optimizing intermediate precision, NIMA enhances MAE performance for both ITA and mixed accumulation schemes, as shown in Figure 4. In contrast, the ETA mirrors the SotA by downsizing intermediate results for on-chip communication, thereby optimizing bandwidth for data transfer at the cost of precision loss during accumulations. Furthermore, the reduced-precision representations in NIMA

TABLE I: Comparison with state-of-the-art

	JSSC'22 [9]	JSSC'23 [10]	Nature Elec.'23 [3]	This Work
Technology	16nm	22nm	14nm	14nm
Frequency (GHz)	0.2	0.05-0.340	0.4	1
Area (kGE)	NA	NA	4495	12.5 (1 NIMA)
Static Power(mW)	NA	NA	1755	4.548 ¹
Latency² (ns)	10	22.2 (@ 0.27GHz)	12.5	4
In-tile Accumulation (ITA)	✓	✓	✗	✓
External Tile Accumulation (ETA)	✓	✗	✓	✓
In/Out Precision	32b	8b	8b	8b
Intermediate Precision	32b	8b	8b	11b
Number of ADCs multiplexed	4	8	128	32
Tot Memory for Accumulation (kB)	0.016	NA	0	0.088

¹Operating conditions: SS, 0.72V, 40°C

NA: Information not available

²Per processing cycle (e.g. multiplexing N ADC) outputs

allow to have a compact and power efficient design, primarily due to the adoption of fixed-precision affine correction logic [8], and the custom intermediate-precision storage mechanism optimized for a predefined number of accumulations (e.g. 7), achieving a threefold reduction in the allocated storage space per ADC compared to [9].

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed NIMA, a fixed-point-based accumulation logic integrated into AIMC tile post-processing logic. NIMA supports both ITA and ETA, providing mapping flexibility to the user while achieving competitive performance compared to the SotA. In addition, we presented and analyzed various mapping schemes, showing that, by adopting a combination of the ITA and ETA schemes, it is possible to achieve a tradeoff between MAE and latency. We also compared the proposed NIMA against traditional approaches adopting DPU tiles to perform simple partial-sum accumulation. In small DNN applications, where only a small number of columns of the tile is used, the proposed NIMA achieves competitive and about $1.6\times$ faster latency while minimizing the MAE compared to traditional approaches adopting specialized DPU, suggesting potential enhancement of the overall latency performance, up to $\times 2.2$ speed-up, when exploiting the full AIMC computing parallelization.

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